

A NOTE ON MERCURY DIALLYL

By K. V. VIJAYARAGHAVAN

The isolation of mercury diallyl by the action of sodium stannite on allyl mercuric iodide has been described by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 589). It has been found that mercury diallyl is also formed by the action of other reagents on allyl mercuric iodide.

On treating allyl mercuric iodide with an excess of a concentrated solution of potassium cyanide the characteristic smell of mercury diallyl was immediately noticed. Gradually all the allyl mercuric iodide disappeared and a colourless heavy liquid settled at the bottom and the aqueous layer was quite clear. The mercury diallyl was extracted with ether. The product was confirmed to be mercury diallyl by adding an ethereal solution of bromine when allyl mercuric bromide was obtained, m.p. 124-25° (decomp.).

It is surprising to note how Oppenheim (*Ber.*, 1871, 4, 671) failed to observe this reaction. Hé reports that by the action of an excess of cold potassium cyanide solution on allyl mercuric iodide mercury, diallyl and a small quantity of a liquid, which explodes on heating, are formed. The smell of the substance is strong enough as not to escape one's notice and it does not explode but merely splits up into mercury and diallyl on heating.

Faint smell of mercury diallyl was noticed on keeping or gently warming aqueous suspensions of freshly prepared allyl mercuric iodide separately with sodium thiosulphate, sodium sulphide and potassium iodide. The action of all these reagents is very slight in the cold. On heating they all decompose allyl mercuric iodide, giving droplets of mercury, and mercury in aqueous solution as the corresponding complex salt. Probably the organic radical is split off.

Alcoholic solutions of allyl mercuric iodide were added to sodium thiosulphate and sodium sulphide separately. The ethereal extracts of these solutions contained no mercury diallyl. No intermediate organo-mercuric compound was present, for on adding sodium stannite, no mercury diallyl was formed. Only mercury was precipitated. The mercury seemed to have been in solution as purely inorganic complex salts, the organic part of the original molecule probably having undergone decomposition. An alcoholic solution of potassium iodide had no action on an alcoholic solution of allyl mercuric iodide in the cold but the smell of mercury diallyl was noticed on gently warming. On heating, the substance underwent decomposition forming potassium mercuric iodide in solution. An acetone solution of sodium iodide also gave a faint smell of mercury diallyl with allyl mercuric iodide in acetone but a greater part of the substance was present unchanged.

The author's thanks are due to Mr. Viswanathan for his kind interest in the work.